

CuO nano flowers – Synthesis and gas sensor application

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Abstract

Air pollution is a growing problem these days. Gas sensors that can identify volatile organic gases (VOCs) or toxic gases are of great importance. Recently, researchers have developed various kinds of gas sensors, such as oxide semiconductors, organic semiconductors, field effect sensors and surface acoustic wave sensors [1,2]. From among the above varieties, oxide semiconductor gas sensors have attracted much attention because of their high sensitivity, low manufacturing cost and simple means of measurement and signal conditioning. Cupric oxide (CuO) is one of the most important p-type oxide semiconductors as it exhibits a stable narrow band gap (1.2–1.9 eV). A simple wet chemical route has been developed for synthesizing cupric oxide (CuO) nanoflowers with excellent reproducibility followed by their utilization in a gas sensor. Copper foil, ammonium persulphate and sodium hydroxide were used as copper precursor, structure directing agent and accelerator, respectively. Characterization studies including x-ray diffraction spectroscopy (XRD), Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), field emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM), and transmission electron microscopy (TEM) were performed to investigate the structure and morphology of the as-synthesized CuO. At the operating temperature of 240 °C, the response/recovery time of the synthesized sensor was measured for acetone. The fabricated CuO nanoflower gas sensor responded very prominently for acetone concentrations of 250 ppm and 2250 ppm and the recorded response was 2.7 and 7.2 respectively. The developed method is a low cost, environmentally friendly and fast route to produce high quality CuO nanoflower gas sensors for VOC's detection.

Keywords: Nanoflower; Oxides semiconductor; Gas sensor; Response/Recovery time

References:

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